

THE ROLE OF VIDEO-BASED ACTIVITIES IN PROMOTING SELF-REGULATED LEARNING IN EFL CLASSROOMS

Djanturayeva Dinara Pardabekovna
Chirchik State Pedagogical University
First -year master`s student
Djanturayevadinara1@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19217296>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th March 2026

Accepted: 22nd March 2026

Online: 24th March 2026

KEYWORDS

video-based learning, self-regulated learning, EFL, motivation, independent learning, learner autonomy

ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the role of video-based activities in developing self-regulated learning among students in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms. Nowadays, modern education focuses not only on knowledge but also on learners' independence and ability to manage their own learning. Self-directed learning entails the processes of planning, monitoring, and evaluating one's own learning activities. The use of video materials in teaching is highly effective due to their ability to combine sound, visuals, and realistic situations. This makes learning more interesting and comprehensible for students. The study was conducted with 8th–9th grade students and used different research methods such as classroom observation, questionnaires, and interviews. The results showed that video-based activities increase students' motivation, help them learn independently, and improve their thinking skills. Students became more active and confident during lessons. It was also noticed that they could better understand the material and remember new information. The study concludes that video-based activities are very effective not only for improving language skills but also for developing self-regulated learning, which is important for students' future education..

Introduction

In recent years, the education system has changed a lot. Traditional teaching methods, where the teacher explains everything and students just listen, are being replaced by modern approaches. Today, students are expected to be more active, independent, and responsible for their own learning.

Among the most widely used skills in modern education is self-controlled learning. Self-controlled learning refers to the ability of learners to set personal goals, plan their learning strategies, monitor their progress, and evaluate their outcomes independently. Students who cultivate this skill often indicate higher academic achievement because they can identify both their capabilities and their limitations. At the same time, technology is becoming a crucial part of academic development. Teachers use different digital tools to

make lessons more interesting and effective. Among various digital tools, video-based resources are considered one of the most effective and widely utilized in modern language instruction. Video materials provide learners with exposure to authentic real-life contexts, accurate pronunciation, and meaningful language use. For example, students can watch conversations, interviews, or short stories in English. This makes learning more natural and engaging.

Based on my personal teaching experience, it has been observed that students show a higher level of engagement when video materials are actively used into lessons. They pay more attention, participate more active, and try to express their ideas.

However, it is important to understand not only how videos help language learning but also how they influence students' ability to learn independently. Therefore, this study focuses on the role of video-based activities in developing self-regulated learning skills among EFL students.

The main aim of this research is to find out how video-based activities affect students' motivation, independence, and learning behavior.

Many researchers have studied self-regulated learning and its importance in education. According to Zimmerman (2002), self-regulated learners are active participants in their learning process. They set goals, choose strategies, and reflect on their results. This helps them become more successful in their studies.

Oxford (2017) explains that self-regulated learning includes different strategies such as thinking, planning, and motivation. Students who use these strategies can control their learning better and become more independent.

Mayer (2009) implemented the concept of multimedia learning. He states that people learn better when information is presented through both visual and auditory channels. This notion reinforces the use of video materials in teaching because videos combine images, sound, and context.

Richards and Renandya (2002) highlight that students need meaningful and real-life input to learn a language effectively. Videos provide authentic language, cultural information, and real communication examples.

Harmer (2019) also emphasizes that videos increase students' interest and motivation. When students watch videos, they become more engaged and understand the material better.

Based on these ideas, it can be said that video-based activities are not only useful for learning English but also help students develop important learning skills such as independence and self-control.

This study used a mixed-method approach, which includes both quantitative and qualitative methods. This approach ensured the collection of more valid and reliable research data.

The research was conducted with 8th–9th grade students in a secondary school. Students were divided into two groups: experimental group (learning with videos), Control group (traditional teaching methods).

The following methods were used: classroom observation, questionnaires, interviews, analysis of students' work, self-assessment forms.

The experimental group was taught using video-based activities for several weeks. Short videos (2–5 minutes) were used during lessons.

After watching videos, students completed different tasks such as answering questions, summarizing the content, discussing in groups, writing their opinions, taking notes. Students were also asked to evaluate their own learning using self-assessment sheets.

The collected data were analyzed using simple statistical methods and thematic analysis. This helped to identify patterns and changes in students' behavior.

The results of the study showed that video-based activities have a strong positive effect on students' learning.

Firstly, students became more motivated. Most of them said that lessons with videos were more interesting and easier to understand. They enjoyed watching videos and were more willing to participate in activities.

Secondly, students developed independent learning skills. They were able to complete tasks without much help from the teacher. They showed more confidence and responsibility for their learning.

Thirdly, students improved their thinking skills. They started to analyze information, express their opinions, and reflect on their learning process.

Another important result is that videos allow students to learn at their own pace. They can pause, replay, and review the content. This helps them understand better and learn more effectively.

In addition, the classroom environment became more active and interactive. Students worked together, shared ideas, and communicated more in English.

These results confirm that video-based learning is very useful not only for language development but also for building self-regulated learning skills.

In conclusion, video-based activities play an important role in modern English language teaching. They help students improve their language skills and become more independent learners.

The study showed that videos increase motivation, develop thinking skills, and support self-regulated learning. Students become more active and responsible for their learning process.

Teachers should use short, interesting, and meaningful videos in their lessons. It is also important to combine videos with interactive tasks and self-assessment activities.

In my opinion, using videos in the classroom is one of the best ways to make lessons more effective and enjoyable. It helps students not only learn English but also develop skills that are important for their future.

Future studies can explore how video-based learning affects students over a longer period of time.

References:

1. Harmer, J. (2019). Teaching and Learning English in the Digital Age.
2. Mayer, R. E. (2009). Multimedia Learning.

3. Oxford, R. (2017). Teaching and Researching Language Learning Strategies.
4. Richards, J. C., & Renandya, W. A. (2002). Methodology in Language Teaching.
5. Zimmerman, B. J. (2002). Becoming a Self-Regulated Learner

